

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

New Rotations: smarter cropping for healthier environments

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

This project will generate quantitative, image and sequence data at field experiment plot resolutions including:

- **Agronomic management data and weather data.**
- **Time series UAV crop imagery.**
- **Soil properties data:** elemental content, nutrient availability, soil carbon fractions, pH, soil-pore structure imagery, and physical properties (e.g. texture, bulk density).
- **Crop data:** yield, yield traits, elemental content, nutrient use efficiency, and crop phenotypic traits.
- **Biodiversity data:** manual invertebrate and botanical surveys.
- **Disease incidence data:** manual disease scores for oilseed rape, oats and wheat.
- **Microbiome sequence data:** generated from rhizosphere, soil, and air samples to identify microbial community phylogeny, structure, and function.
- **Simulation data:** from statistical and process-based models plus associated code.

II. Standards and metadata

Core metadata plus logged deviations, will be captured using FarmOS. FarmOS provides automatic ontological annotation of terms, for example plant experimental conditions ontology for annotating treatment factors. Plots and samples will be allocated an IGSN (igsn.org) identifier. Each IGSN will provide plot or sample metadata and datasets will be expected to reference source IGSNs. Methods and procedures will be documented using protocols.io and surveys and experiments recorded in electronic lab notebooks, including details of capturing instrument metadata. A curated variable list referencing public ontologies is maintained to ensure variables are consistently described and interoperable with other studies.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Models will additionally combine primary data with publicly available data from the Rothamsted Long-term Experiments (era.rothamsted.ac.uk) and Earlham Institute Grassroots (grassroots.tools/fieldtrial).

IV. Secondary use

Data will be freely available permitting reuse by the wider research community.

V. Methods for data sharing

Soil microbiome sequence data will be published to the ENA and analysed using MGnify (ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics). Soil sample metadata will be publicly accessible via locally hosted IGSN landing pages. Crop phenotyping and traits data, and soils data be published to either the institute data repository or NERC EIDC (eidc.ac.uk). Source code on Github will be published to the Zenodo repository. Datasets will be published under Creative Commons Attribution Licence conditions. Code will be published with a open source software licence.

VI. Proprietary data

There are no restrictions to data sharing.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be collected over a 5-year period, therefore for each year's data there will be a 3 year period of exclusive use during which data will be embargoed.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

- **Sequence data** >15TB, saved as FASTQ formats.
- **UAV imagery data**: ~1TB raw imagery and transformed orthomosaics as TIFF and JPG formats.
- **X-Ray CT 3D imagery**: ~500 GB, raw imagery will be saved in TIFF format.
- **Quantitative data** extracted from UAV and X-Ray CT imagery will be stored as CSV.
- **Farm management and plot layout data** as JSON and GeoJSON respectively. ~1MB

All other datasets will be generated as tabular data and formatted as either CSV and Excel formats following Tidy Data principles. < 100MB